

Synthesis and Spectral Studies of some New Fluorinated Phosphonium Salts and Ylides

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THE phosphonium ylides constitute an important class of precursors in synthetic organophosphorus chemistry¹. In view of the unique behaviour of organic-fluorine, it was thought of interest to prepare some new fluorinated phosphonium ylides and study their reactions.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of triphenylphosphine with 2-fluoro-5-methylphenacyl bromide (1a) and 4-fluorophenacyl bromide (1b) in dry toluene at reflux temperature afforded (2-fluoro-5-methylphenacyl)-triphenylphosphonium bromide (2a) and (4-fluorophenacyl)triphenylphosphonium bromide (2b) in good yields (Scheme 1).

The physical and spectral data of 2a–b are shown in Table 1. In the ir spectra, a sharp band at

1 655–1 665 cm⁻¹ is observed due to ν_{C=O} stretch. In ¹H nmr spectra, a doublet at δ 6.25–6.58 appears due to methylene protons while aromatic protons absorb at δ 6.7–8.1; methyl protons of 2a absorb at δ 2.3. In ¹⁹F nmr spectra, 2a and 2b gave singlets at δ -100.24 and -101.07, while in ³¹P nmr spectra, signals are observed at δ 23.48 and 20.88, respectively. These values are in the range reported earlier². In mass spectral studies of 2a, a very weak molecular ion (m/z 493) splits off hydrogen bromide to form the ion at m/z 412, which corresponds to the parent ion emanating from the corresponding ylide molecule. The onward fragmentation of this ion (m/z 412) occurs similar to that of the ylide discussed later.

The phosphonium salts on treatment with sodium ethoxide in dry toluene afforded the corresponding ylides (3a–b) in crystalline form (Scheme 2).

The physical and spectral data of 3a–b are summarised in Table 1. In the ir spectra, the carbonyl stretching band as expected suffers a red-shift and is observed at 1 580–1 585 cm⁻¹. In the ¹H nmr spectra, aromatic protons absorb at δ 6.7–8.1 whereas methine proton in 3b exhibited a doublet at δ 4.4 ppm (²J_{PCH} 24 Hz). However, in 3a, the signal for the methine proton could not be observed which may be attributed to the fast proton exchange as reported by Randall and Johnson³. In ¹⁹F nmr spectra, the products 3a–b give sharp singlets at δ -114.22 and -111.84 while the ³¹P signals are

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 2a, b AND 3a, b

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		ν _{C=O} cm ⁻¹	δ*	m/z (%)
				C	H			
2a	82	221	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ POBrF	65.21 (65.71)	4.86 (4.66)	1 655	2.3(3H, s, CH ₃), 6.25(2H, d, CH ₂), ² J _{PCH} 12 Hz), 6.7–8.1(18H, m, Ar)	492(M ⁺ -1, 2.7), 412(100), 411(99.5), 383(12.3), 303(99.5), 277(54.8), 275(18.1), 262(35.5), 185(18.1), 183(70.9), 108(5.1)
2b	84	260	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ POBrF	65.19 (65.29)	4.12 (4.39)	1 665	6.58(2H, d, ² J _{PCH} 14 Hz, CH ₂), 7.1–8.8(19H, m, Ar)	—
3a	74	126	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ POF	77.83 (78.60)	5.85 (5.34)	1 585	2.25(3H, s, CH ₃), 6.7–8.0(18H, m, Ar)	412(M ⁺ , 100), 411(99.5), 383(18.1), 303(99.5), 277(48.7), 275(18.7), 262(18.7), 185(19.6), 183(19.6), 108(51.0)
3b	72	181	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ POF	78.46 (78.44)	5.04 (5.02)	1 580	4.4(1H, d, ² J _{PCH} 24 Hz, CH), 6.9–8.1(19H, m, Ar)	—

*¹H nmr spectra.

Fluorinated phosphonium salts (2a-b): A solution of triphenylphosphine and the appropriate fluoro-phenacyl bromide (0.022 mol) in anhydrous toluene (40 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. The resulting phosphonium salt was filtered off, washed with toluene, dried and recrystallised from chloroform-ether.

Fluorinated phosphonium ylides (3a-b): To a stirred suspension of the phosphonium salt (0.01 mol) in dry toluene (50 ml) was added sodium ethoxide (0.05 mol). The mixture was stirred for 30 h and filtered off. Toluene was removed under reduced pressure and hexane was added to precipitate the ylide. The ylides were recrystallised from toluene-hexane.

Reaction of ylides with aromatic aldehydes: To a solution of the ylide (0.003 mol) in anhydrous toluene was added aromatic aldehyde (0.003 mol) and the mixture was heated at about 80° for 50 h. Toluene was then removed and the products were separated by column chromatography using alumina.

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A New Synthesis of Aroyl Cyanides from Phenacyl Bromides

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1-Amino-4,6-diphenyl-2-pyridene^{1,2} (1) and **1-amino-4,6-diphenyl-2-thioxo-1,2-dihydropyridine³ (2)** have been reported as reagents for the facile conversion of aldehydes into nitriles by pyrolysis of the aldimine intermediates. The work also has been extended⁴ for a convenient alternative synthesis of aromatic and aliphatic nitriles (6) from the aldehydes (4) via pyrolysis of aldimines (5) derived from 3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazolines (3)

(Chart 1). The aldimines are readily prepared by the reaction of 3 with aromatic aldehydes and the reaction is completed at the boiling point of the solvent employed. The conversion 5→6+7, involves fission of the N-N bond and the process is facilitated by an intramolecular transfer in which the carbonyl group acts as an internal base.

We report herein a rapid and facile one-pot reaction for the conversion of phenacyl bromides into aroyl nitriles by the use of 2-aryl-3-amino-4-oxo-3,4-dihydroquinazolinone (3) (where aryl R¹ = C₆H₅, C₆H₅CH₂) in DMSO. The reaction of 3 with phenacyl bromides in hot DMSO gave on subsequent workup the aroyl cyanides (9) in appreciable yields. The reaction presumably proceeds via the formation of aldimines (8) intermediate generated from 3 and the unstable arylglyoxal⁵ produced in the reaction medium. Under the reaction conditions, the aldimine (8) intermediate is pyrolysed to give a mixture of aroyl cyanide (9) and 4(3H)-quinazolinone (7) (Chart 2). The aroyl cyanide thus formed could be easily separated from the reaction mixture in hot benzene. The ir spectra of aroyl cyanides show strong intense peaks at 2230-2280 (C≡N) and 1680 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

